

Volume 10, Number 1, December, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM VOL.10, NUMBER 1, DECEMBER, 2024

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

A Publication of

**THE DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY AND
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT,
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCE,
UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN,
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VOLUME 10, NUMBER 1, DECEMBER, 2024

ISSN: 1596-4116

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HEAVY METALS IN UNTREATED WASTEWATER AND SOIL FOR IRRIGATION: A PUBLIC HEALTH CONCERN IN JERE LGA, BORNO STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract: Heavy metals constitute one of the major causes of contamination in the environment resulting from natural geological events and human activities. Most heavy metals have very long residence time. The presence of heavy metals in untreated wastewater and soil used for crop production could constitute serious public health risk as the heavy metals are readily absorbed by vegetables. Irrigation farming is a major preoccupation in the study area, hence the study. Fifty samples each of untreated wastewater and soil were collected from ten (10) locations in the study area by convenient sampling. The samples were analyzed for heavy metals by digestion and atomic absorption spectrophotometric (AAS) techniques. Result obtained indicates that the overall mean concentrations of Cu, Fe, Cr, Pb, Zn, Ni and Mn detected in the wastewater samples were 1.44 ± 0.44 , 1.59 ± 0.32 , 0.28 ± 0.08 , 1.58 ± 0.82 , 1.19 ± 0.29 , 0.63 ± 0.12 and 1.02 ± 0.22 mg/L respectively, and all these values are significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the WHO permissible levels. Similarly, the overall mean levels of Cu, Cr, Zn and Ni in soil samples were significantly above ($p < 0.05$) the permissible limits while Fe and Mn were normal. The study revealed the presence of heavy metals in both the wastewater and soil samples at levels above the WHO permissible limits. The high levels portend a serious environmental and health risk which requires urgent attention and interventions by relevant stakeholders.

Keywords: Heavy metals, wastewater, soil, irrigation, Public health risk

INTRODUCTION

Heavy metals are metals with specific gravity greater than 4g/cm^3 . They include; lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), and manganese (Mn). Naturally, heavy metals may result from natural geological events

such as earthquakes and volcanic eruptions, or from human activities including mining, smelting, use of agrochemicals and disposal of industrial and domestic wastes. Heavy metals affect the environment in many ways; they contaminate, affect soil nutrient balance resulting in deficiency of soil micronutrient cations, may be toxic to living organisms and may be absorbed by

vegetable plants and be introduced into the food chain (Jarup, 2003).

Wastewater consists of a mixture of domestic effluent, encompassing black water (comprising excreta, urine, and fecal sludge) and grey water (including wastewater from kitchens and bathing), as well as water from commercial establishments, institutions, hospital, agricultural, horticultural and aquaculture activities. These effluents can exist as dissolved or suspended matter (Corcoran, 2010). Wastewater contains potentially toxic elements (PTEs) such as Zinc (Zn), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Cadmium (Cd), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb), Mercury (Hg), as well as parasitic worms, posing significant risks to both human health and the environment (Mark *et al.*, 2017). Untreated wastewater used for irrigation can contribute to soil hardening and contamination of shallow groundwater (Muamar *et al.*, 2014). Proper management and disposal of wastewater thus constitutes a serious environmental challenge especially in urban centers where wastewater is generated in large quantities and eventually get emptied into bodies of freshwater. The discharge of industrial effluents and agricultural waste into water bodies particularly stand out as prominent causes of environmental pollution and degradation, especially in developing countries where adequate regulations for liquid and solid waste disposal are lacking. Such waste may contaminate the environment posing risks of infection, toxicity, or even radioactivity (Mshelizah *et al.*, 2017). According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2012), only about 20% of wastewater generated worldwide undergoes proper treatment. This treatment capacity is significantly higher for developed nations, reaching 70%, while it is alarmingly low at 8% for developing countries. Consequently, about 1.8 billion people are exposed to drinking water

sources contaminated with heavy metals, fecal matter and disease-causing organisms which could place them at high risk of contracting diseases such as cholera, dysentery, typhoid, and polio (UN-Water, 2016). Conversely, effective wastewater treatment before disposal or use for irrigation would mitigate these risks and safeguard public health. Similarly, effective measures of soil treatment to remove heavy metal contamination of arable land are recommended before cultivation (WHO, 1979; WHO, 2016).

In soil, the heavy metals have very long residence time in the environment and may last for few hundred years (Kabata-Pendias, 1992). The presence of heavy metals in agricultural soil and untreated wastewater used for growing crops constitutes a serious public health risk. The metals could be introduced into the food chain when vegetables are grown in contaminated environment because they readily absorb heavy metals into their tissues. This has informed some policy decisions hence, the setting of WHO (1989; 2016) permissible levels of heavy metals in agricultural soil and irrigation water in order to mitigate the health risks. In the study area, irrigation farming using wastewater is a major preoccupation of the locals along river Nggaga, this is because it is cheaper and rich in nutrients. Study by Zhang *et al.*, (2017) has shown that wastewater application offers significant quantities of macronutrients such as Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), and Potassium (K) to the soil and plants (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). Consequently, there is a strong allure for impoverished farmers to utilize wastewater for crop irrigation, as it presents an opportunity to reduce production costs (Scott *et al.*, 2010). Irrigation farming provides a significant portion of the vegetables consumed in Maiduguri and environs. Thus, the study was done to ascertain the levels of heavy metals in soil

and untreated wastewater used for irrigation farming in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS
STUDY AREA

The study area comprised a section of River Ngadda at the upstream of the Jere Bowl, Maiduguri. This area can be found between longitude 13° 10' 14.839" and 13° 11' 2.274" East of the Greenwich meridian and between latitudes 11°49' 55.99" and 11°50' 14.839" North of the equator. The Jere Bowl is found some 15 kilometers northeast of Maiduguri and covers 15,000

hectares of land. Rainy season in the study area spans from May to October with mean monthly rainfall above 50mm seen between June to September and peak in August (193 mm). The mean monthly minimum and maximum temperature is usually observed in the month of December (13.5 °C) and April (40.2 °C) respectively (Shettima, 2019). The study area was originally a region of swampland fed by the Ngadda River. Like other wetlands, it has an integrated farming system, fishing and pastoral economy. The study area is a major irrigation site where wastewater is used extensively.

Figure 1.1 The Study Area

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 50 water and soil samples each were collected during the dry season (November to April) at a distance of 150m apart in 10 sampling points along the river channel taking five (5) samples per location and labeled accordingly. The soil samples were systematically collected following Ogunmwoyi *et al.* (2008) at a depth of 7.5cm using 8.5cm diameter auger at positions where irrigation farming is being carried out. Laboratory analyses were subsequently carried out at department of Soil science, University of Maiduguri and NAFDAC Chemistry laboratory Maiduguri, using standard methods of digestion and atomic absorption spectrophotometry following Rhoades (1982).

The collected soil samples were dried using hot oven (Model 30GC lab oven) and then ground into fine powder using a porcelain mortar and pestle. 100mg of each sample was weighed into thoroughly clean plastic container (microwave tube) and 6ml of 65% HNO₃, 3ml of HF and 3mL of HCl were added and the mixture was covered and placed in to microwave digester (Master 40 serial No: 40G106M), where it was digested at an initial temperature of 130⁰C and then ramped to 210⁰C for 30 mins. The digestion was followed by a cooling to room temperature in the microwave. Potential presence of heavy metals in chemicals used in digestion were determined. Blanks were used simultaneously in each batch of the analysis to authenticate the analytical quality. The digested samples were diluted with deionized water to a total volume of 25ml. 100ppm working solution was then prepared from the stock solution by simple dilution using 1mL of concentrated HNO₃ and deionised water.

Calibration curves were prepared by appropriate dilutions of the working solutions (at concentration of mg/ml) and were used to determine the concentration of the metals in the sample solution. The AAS was calibrated using series of working standards. The working standard solutions of each metal were prepared from their respective standard solutions and their absorbencies were measured. Calibration curve for each metal ion was finally prepared by plotting the absorbance as a function of metal ion standard concentration.

Concentration of the metal ions present in the sample was determined in triplicates by reading their absorbance using AAS (Buck scientific model 210GP) and comparing it with the respective standard calibration curve. The metals concentrations were determined in the absorption/concentration mode by taking the readings on the instrument. The same analytical procedure was employed for the determination of elements in digested blank solutions, wastewater samples and for the spiked samples.

The laboratory results were subsequently analysed using the IBM statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 20). The one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the means and mean difference between variables. Results were presented as means and standard deviations using tables and bar charts. Statistical significance was inferred at $p < 0.05$

RESULTS

The concentrations of heavy metals in the untreated wastewater samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1a: Mean Concentrations of Heavy Metals in Untreated Wastewater of River Ngadda

Parameter	Overall Mean ±SD (mg/L)	WHO Standard Values(mg/L)
Copper	1.44±0.44	1
Iron	1.59±0.32	0.3
Chromium	0.28±0.08	0.05
Lead	1.58±0.82	0.01
Zinc	1.19±0.29	0.01
Nickel	0.63±0.12	0.02
Manganese	1.02±0.22	0.02

Source: WHO, 2016

Table 1b: Statistical Summary for Concentrations of Heavy Metals in Untreated Wastewater along River Ngadda

Parameter	Sum of Squares (Between)	df (Between)	Mean Square (Between)	F-value	Sig.
Copper	54.073	9	6.008	19.501	0.000
Iron	61.215	9	6.802	31.117	0.000
Chromium	1.951	9	0.217	28.037	0.000
Lead	55.614	9	6.179	4.777	0.000
Zinc	43.856	9	4.873	39.225	0.000
Nickel	36.52	9	4.058	3.099	0.006
Manganese	44.435	9	4.937	30.808	0.000

Source: IBM SPSS Statistical results

NB: The Statistical parameters were similarly determined for the mean levels of heavy metals in the soil samples

Figure 1: Overall mean concentration of heavy metals in untreated wastewater samples in the study area

The levels of heavy metals in agricultural soil samples collected from different locations along River Ngadda are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean levels of Heavy Metals in Soil Samples along River Ngadda

Parameter	Overall Mean \pm SD (mg/L)	WHO Standard Values(mg/kg)
Copper	10.7 \pm 2.2	3.5
Iron	18.2 \pm 6.5	50
Chromium	5.7 \pm 2.9	3.8
Lead	6.5 \pm 2.0	55
Zinc	29.3 \pm 10.9	16
Nickel	3.7 \pm 0.9	2.6
Manganese	19.0 \pm 6.8	200

Figure 2: Overall mean level of heavy metals in agricultural soil of the study area

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed the level of heavy metals in soil and untreated wastewater along river Ngadda where agricultural activities are predominantly carried out in Jere LGA of Maiduguri, Borno state. Besides the use of wastewater for irrigation in the study area, other uses observed include; washing of edible vegetables before taking to market, drinking by domestic animals, washing of cloths and other household materials, and use in building construction works. The study observed that the sources of wastewater in the study area include effluents from the nearby Maiduguri abattoir and domestic wastes. In the wastewater examined, the overall mean concentrations of the seven screened heavy metals Cu, Fe, Cr, Pb, Zn, Ni and Mn were 1.44 ± 0.44 , 1.59 ± 0.32 , 0.28 ± 0.08 , 1.58 ± 0.82 , 1.19 ± 0.29 , 0.63 ± 0.12 and 1.02 ± 0.22 mg/ml respectively and all these values were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the WHO (2016) permissible limits.

In the soil samples, the overall mean levels of Cu, Cr, Zn and Ni were 10.7 ± 2.2 , 5.7 ± 2.9 , 29.3 ± 10.9 and 3.7 ± 0.9 mg/Kg respectively. These values were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than their permissible limits. However, the levels of Fe, Cu and Pb were normal. These findings are similar to that of Ibrahim *et al.*, (2022) who reported high levels of heavy metals in wastewater samples from Monday market, Coca Cola and abattoir in Maiduguri. In the present study, the levels of the heavy metals in wastewater samples were higher than their permissible levels by many folds (about twice for Cu, 5 times for Fe and Cr, 30 times for Ni, 50 times for manganese, 120 times for Zn and 150 times for Pb). The high values of heavy metals observed in this study could be related to the aforementioned sources of the wastewater, soil composition and the nature of human activities in the study area.

High concentration of the heavy metals in the wastewater is of concern to the environment, animal and human health as most heavy metals are readily absorbed by vegetables and thus enter the food chain. Disturbingly, most of these heavy metals exhibit toxicity even at lower concentrations, and their build-up in body tissues over a period of time could be detrimental to human health (Mojeed, 2020). According to Omer (2019), Cu in small concentration is nontoxic, essential and beneficial for human health and growth of plants and animals but causes undesirable taste in drinking water at high concentration. The Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2007) highlighted gastrointestinal disorders as the major health impact of high concentration of copper in water. Similarly, Abagale *et al.* (2013) stated that at concentrations slightly above those required as a micronutrient, copper becomes toxic especially to the larval stages of marine invertebrates. The United State Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2020) attributed damages to nervous system, impaired hearing and malfunction of blood cells to lead exposure from water and food.

In human and animals, the common means of Pb exposure include the ingestion of lead contaminated water, vegetables and other food items. High level of Pb observed in this study could pose environmental and health risks that may result into Pb toxicity. Environmental exposure to Pb is a serious public health concern and could result in lead toxicity associated with chronic health conditions such as nerve damage, paralysis, cancer, renal failure, impaired cognitive function and infertility in humans even with small amount of Pb in food or water (Samco, 2021). Besides the effect on human and animal, accumulation of Pb in soil inhibit plant growth significantly (Samco, 2021). The impact of Nickel (Ni) in the environment includes green house emission, destruction of habitat and contamination of water, soil and air. Ni was ranked amongst the top most

damaging metal to human health and the ecosystem especially with its effects on global warming (Gupta *et al.*, 2016). Areas with high level of chromium could impact human negatively as plants grown around such environment could be toxic to man (Gupta *et al.*, 2016) and exposure to high concentration of chromium in food and water can lead to cancer (SON, 2007). Iron is the most essential element for growth and development of most living organisms and also the second most available element on earth (Valko *et al.*, 2005). However, high concentration of iron in wastewater contributes to soil acidification and loss of availability of phosphorus and molybdenum when applied to the soil. Risk analyses conducted on aquatic and soil environments suggested that present-day zinc levels do not pose a risk to the environment. (Abagale, *et al.*, 2013).

CONCLUSION

The study revealed higher concentrations of heavy metals in the wastewater samples which were all above their permissible limits. Similarly, higher levels of Cr, Ni, Cu and Zn were found in the soil samples while the levels of Fe, Pb and Mn were normal. The high levels of the heavy metals in wastewater and agricultural soil portend a serious environmental and health risk which requires urgent attention of relevant stakeholders.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Further studies are required to determine the levels of heavy metals in vegetables and fruits grown by irrigation farming along the study area.
2. Environmental health workers should enlighten the farmers on the dangers of using untreated wastewater to feed domestic animals and for growing and washing of edible vegetables.

3. Soil scientists and relevant stakeholders should intervene by ensuring soil and water quality used especially for irrigation agriculture.

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